
DEVELOPMENT AND DISPLACEMENT: A CASE STUDY OF DAPCHARI VILLAGE IN PALGHAR DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Process of development has resulted in problem of environmental imbalance and various concerns damaging environment and creating issues related future environmental protection. Dams are built across valley to store water for sole or multipurpose. They provide various benefits from recreational facilities to revenue generation, helping farming or preventing floods. Dams have always been very important in process of development. One of main reasons to construct a dam is to satisfy everyday need of water for domestic use as well as to provide water for agriculture purpose. Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru used to call them “Temples of Morden India”. Although there are benefits of dam construction, but in the context of climate change and growing global demand for electricity, recent experience has shown that many dams have serious negative environmental, human, and political consequences.

Thus, construction of dams also results in environmental refugees. The present research is an empirical study of environmental refugees and their impact on climate change. The present paper is the case study of Dapchhari and Khuballa village of Palghar district of Maharashtra.

This study focuses on problems faced by environmental migrants and effect on their life in various sphere

Key words: *Environmental refugees, sustainable development, displacement effects*

Introduction

Guaranteeing the balance between economic growth, care for the environment and social well-being that satisfies the needs of the present without compromising the capacity of future generations shall be termed to be sustainable development.

Dams are built across valley to store water for sole or multipurpose. They provide various benefits from recreational facilities to revenue generation, helping farming or preventing floods. Dams has always been very important in process of development. But one of the main reasons to construct a dam is to satisfy everyday need of water for domestic use as well as to provide water for agriculture purpose. Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru used to call them “Temples of Morden India”. Although there are benefits of dam construction, but in the context of climate change and growing global demand for electricity, recent experience has shown that many dams have serious negative environmental, human, and political consequences.

A drastic change in river composition can affect environment in a bad way. Dams disturbs fish and bird's migration as it disrupts chemical signals which guides the species through their biological process. Dam walls block these species from spawning and rearing process. Reservoirs those in tropical regions, emit significant amounts of greenhouse gases because of anaerobic bacteria that break down the vegetation at the base of the reservoir, giving off carbon dioxide and methane.

Building dams not only affects flora fauna but also the people staying in the villages around the dams. Around 80 million people worldwide are displaced for building dams. The people removed from dam building sites or the people who lose their homes to failing dams, most of the displaced communities come

from underprivileged areas already affected by climate change. This also promotes crimes in the society as migrants are ill-treated by the locals of the area

Objectives of the Study

- To understand concept/process of development in Indian.
- To understand problems faced by displaced people i.e. environmental refugees after their migration.
- To observe the phenomenon of climate change due to development.

Review of Literature

Environmental Change and Security Program argues that the international community should focus its efforts on building a framework to address the climate related migration and displacement impacts of disappearing islands and withdrawing coastlines. The short post suggests that understanding the drivers of climate related displacement and taking care to understand the political dimensions and avoid attaching displacement to purely “natural” phenomena is key in developing and implementing timely interferences, including planned relocations. This briefly blog helpfully situates involvements such as planned relocations within the broader discussion of the concept of “climate refugees” and offers suggestions of what policy makers, particularly in the United States, can do to address this phenomenon.

Paper first presents the background to and context of current discussions and approaches surrounding climate change-related human mobility across borders in Part one. In Part two before identifying the normative gaps in the present international protection regime together with institutional and operational shortcomings. It argues that while a relationship between climate change, environmental events and displacement/migration exists, direct causalities are difficult to establish. Rather, such movements are triggered by multiple causes.

The concept of sustainable development and its various phases of development since the introduction are discussed. Th historical development of concept of participation of various organisation and institution on the implementation of its principle are conversed in this article. The concept has experienced different criteria and interpretation over time while being accepted in different areas of human activity. The development concept has been adapting to the contemporary requirement of a complex global environment. But the underlying principles and goals as well as the problems of their implementation are defined briefly

Sustainable Development Atlas 2017

countries or to measure progress. The cut-off date for data included in this is March 30, 2018. The 2018 Atlas uses two primary methods for classifying and aggregating countries and economies by income as mentioned for the World Bank’s 2018 fiscal year and by_region

The Paris Agreement 2016

India, the world’s third largest emitter of greenhouse gases, on October 2, ratified the landmark Paris climate deal, giving a major boost to the deal which appeared tantalisingly close to enter into force by the end of this year. the Paris Agreement on climate change ever closer to its entry into force, India today joined the new global accord at the UN Headquarters and became the 62nd country to deposit its legal instrument of ratification. The International Day of Non-violence, marked every year on Gandhi’s birth anniversary, Ban said there is no better way to commemorate Gandhi and his legacy for people and the planet than with India submitting its instrument of ratification of the Paris agreement on climate change.

Sustainable development summit 2015

The UN 2030 agenda for sustainable development was published setting up 17 millennium development goals of sustainable development goals which should be achieved by 2030

UN conference Rio

Twenty years from Rio conference report the future we want renewed the commitment to the global sustainable development and encourage the issue of global green economy.

Importance of Study

The empirical study on environmental migrant and climate change in the village of Dapchari, district Dahanu helps to learn how necessary it is to maintain balance between environment label and development. The building of dam was necessary for conservation of water which will lead to development but it also has an adverse impact on the environment of the local area. The area is prone to unpredictable rainstorm or drought where the water is not able to reach some times. People in the locality are experiencing minor earthquakes during the day and also the night. Many cracks in the mountain can be seen which increased the risk of land sliding and cause threat to lives.

Research Methodology

An empirical research was conducted to understand various problems of migrants and locals of the place where these migrants were moved a questionnaire was made and both the sides were interviewed

The main focus of this research was to understand the problems faced by the migrants. Through an active member of the NGO that helps supporting people of Dapchari and Kojbaad village to get their lives back on track helped understanding the issues faced by the people. Various details were provided by him regarding the project and its impact. By using interview method of affected people and other stakeholders' information is collected and analytical study is done.

Secondary data is used for review of literature and other references.

Limitation of Study

Due to lack of written evidence and non-availability of records of the migrants presently residing researcher faced problems to take interview of affected people. However, related information was collected by telephonic conversations with one of the NGO representatives.

Case Study of Dapchari Village

Located on the west near the Konkan coast of Maharashtra's Dahanu taluka the village of Dapchari with population not more than 4000 people mainly belonging to "Naavtar Tribe" and "Aadivasi Tribe". Along with Dapchari, Khoballa village was also asked to shift from their villages for a government-initiated project of construction of a Dam. According to sources, In the year 1976, When Maharashtra Agriculture Lands (ceiling on holding) Act 1961 was passed by parliament, in which any person is not allowed to hold property of more than 54 Acer and will have to surrender his excess property to the government.

With an intension to avoid the losses of land the moneylender of the village named Dapchari proposed the government officials a project of building Dam in Dapchari village. this would benefit him by selling his land to government for dam construction project and cash his property instead of giving land to the farmers. The project was approved by government and the plan was executed accordingly.

In the year 1970 the villagers received an order from government regarding vacating of village for construction of a Dam. The government officials announced building of dam and informed people to vacant the place a year ago. These people were supposed to shift to Mannor, Kosbaad-Boroda, Navi Dapchari, Karjat. They were promised to be given place for housing and farming in exchange to their lands, and other infrastructural facilities by government in exchange to their properties in Dapchari and Khoballa village which will now be used to construct Dam. No written assurance or agreement was given to the people regarding allotted land or housing after migration. Numerous problems were faced by the local people during and after migration. Some people had to even leave the land and houses allotted by the government as they

were tortured by the local people in that area. Some land provided by the government were not suitable for agriculture. People face lots of problem regarding food, employment, dwelling, vaccinations, etc.

Approximate Information of families who were migrated from Dapchari Village is given as follows:

Villages Families Were Sent To	No. of Families
Uplap, Patil Pada	20 Families
Uplap, Nava Pada	10 Families
Zari Karvandi Pada	10 Families
Talasari, Barat Pada	20 Families
Vadoli, Nava Pada	10 Families
Dhamangaon, Zhaadi Pada	10 Families
Purze, Lohar Pada	10 Families
Puze, Zambhron Pada	10 Families
Shilonda	5 Families
Navi Dapchari, Kojbaad	20 Families
Boronda, Kosbaad	10 Families
Kharanji, Wada	13 Families
Kuiloo, Wada	10 Families
Mannor	13 Families
Talasari, Paras Pada	5 Families

Out of which Families who got land from government in Boronda Village, Kosbaad were in bad condition and were not suitable for agriculture. The Thirteen families shifted to Mannor had to come back to Dapchari Village because of ill-treatment by the local people in Mannor. Migrants generally face many problems and between these problems several personal rights are violated. Rights such as right to equality was violated as they were illtreated because they were outsiders. Basic rights Just like a plant, the type of surrounding and the environmental conditions determines its growth. If that plant is uprooted and planted somewhere else without proper care and nurturing, the plant may not get accustomed to its new surrounding and may die. Hence even though sometimes the need arises for the location of that plant to be changed. Proper care and conditioning of the plant to its new environment is important. Similarly, in case of people when there is lack to care and nurturing like providing necessities can gives rise to various problem like rise in criminal activities and negativity among the general people, Depletion of resources, etc.

This project not only had adverse impact on the people residing in nearby villages but also there were seen several effects on the environment. The area is facing unpredictable climate change. Problems of drought are faced by the general public. The area has become an earthquake prone zone. Several times Minor level of earthquakes are experienced by people. There are huge cracks in the mountains in Dapchari area, which has increased the risk of land sliding.

Findings

To understand the effects of such development projects on the general population few interviews were taken

of people who migrated from their homes and following things were observed. Following are the observations from the interviews.

- Maximum people belong to lower class and economically unstable families.
- People who were interviewed were either from Naavtar or Adivasi tribe initially from Dapchari village and moved to Talasari later due to a government-initiated project of dam construction
- Since the research focus on problems of migrants all the people who were interviewed were the locals of Dapchari village.
- There were many problems faced by the people during and after migration like:
 1. Problems while shifting to village allotted by government officials
 2. Housing issues
 3. Employment issues
 4. Food problems
 5. Agricultural land problems
 6. Attitude of locals towards migrants, etc
- Some people received help and support from the government and some because of illiteracy or other reasons got unsatisfactory help from the government.

A few numbers of interviews helped the researcher to understand that there were many problems faced by the migrants. But it was also necessary to understand the outlook of the locals towards migrants. Therefore, some interview was conducted by the researcher. Researcher has taken interview of 15 general people who are locals of the area they are residing into.

Hence, following are given some of the diagrams that describe point of view of local people regarding environment refugees are given:

Are you aware about the about the problems due to migration?

15 responses

- Maximum (87%) people are aware about the problem arising due to migration in various cities or towns.
- But still few people have not even realised the problems arising because of migration. These are 13% of the total interview.

Do you think problem of migration is affecting your area?

15 responses

- Almost all people are facing these problems in their life.
- 93% of people are getting affected by the overpopulation in their local areas might be due to their job or increase in competition
- Rest 7% people do not have confidence that problem of migration is not affecting their area much. Which is very less

How serious you think it is on the scale of 0-5?

15 responses

- All the people think it is serious issue
- 33% people think it is average serious
- Maximum people meaning 47% of them think it is above average serious.
- Rest 20% of the people think its very serious and some actions should be taken against it.

What problems you personally felt because of migrants?

15 responses

- Some problems and effects of migration were given to the people and given above are the results of their answers.
- Maximum people have been affected by increase in population and increasing criminal activities.
- After that next it affects the environment of the place people have migrated to.
- After these issues people are concerned about depletion of resources and securities issue.
- And very less people think migration increases unemployment among locals and improve infrastructural development.

Are u aware what an environmental migrant is?

15 responses

- It is a huge problem that almost 47% of people have no idea what an environmental migrant.
- But more people atleast know the meaning of environmental migrants that is 53%

Are there some in your nearby area?

15 responses

- 60% of people are not sure that whether the migrants residing in their areas had displaced because of environmental reasons or due to some other reason.
- Whereas 13% of people don't even know that one of the reasons of people coming to their place could be bad environmental conditions at their home land.
- People who know that migrants living near their locality have come because of environmental issues are 26%.

Do u know what problem are faced by them?

15 responses

- Almost 67% of people have no idea what problems are faced by the people around them regarding environmental issues.
- Very less people (33%) of people know regarding environmental refugees.

Observations from findings:

During the empirical research it was observed by the researcher that majority of the people whether literate or not, knows the problems and issues of migrants. Migrants not really seem to be comfortable by leaving their houses and settling some place else. They are not even readily welcomed by the locals in the new place.

Regarding local people many specifically people are unaware about environment migration and do not even know the problems faced by them. They actually are ignorant that moving of these migrants to their area was not their choice but their necessity. This might be one of the reasons that locals do not treat people migrated from another place with same love and care as they treat other locals.

It was observed that migration was not choice of the people but they had to migrate because of the circumstances. Building of dam didn't seem really that productive instead it added to environmental damage. Unpredicted climatic change has added up to the problems of the general population in the nearby area. The idea of sustainable development seems to be slightly neglected in this case.

Conclusion

Development of the state or a country is one of the main motives of the administrative leaders. No doubt a state can develop fast when it has abundant water to fulfil its day to day needs. As it is rightly said in Sanskrit "*Su Jalam Su Phalam*". Sufficient water increases the scope for industrialisation which brings in profits. This leads to the development and prosperity of the state. But when they are primarily focusing on the developmental aspects only the environmental balance can be disturbed. As in case of Dapchhari village which force the local people to migrate to different places to avoid the threat to the life. Therefore, the concept of sustainable development should be taken seriously in every developmental project

Suggestions

- Any project should be adopted when analysed properly and undertake with responsibility of taking care of various factors like its local's displacement, the amenities provided to them, the compensation paid to the people, etc.

- Before beginning the project its impact on the environment should be forecast beforehand and if the project has an adverse impact on the environment certain changes should be made in the project which would reduce the risk of harming the environment.
- Some provisions for the migrants who have to move because of adverse climatic or unfavourable environmental conditions near their residential area.
- Awareness regarding environmental migrants and their problems must be given to the general public to improve and help these migrants to recover their lives back. Migrants should get same dignity and respect as any other people get in the society.
- We all must strive and together try to conserve our natural resources and reduce the damage to the environment by finding a totally different path of development which will help us conserve and restore our environment.

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